

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE QUALITY OF BRIDGE PROSTHESIS WITH IMPLANT SUPPORT

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Abstract

To study the functional effectiveness of bridge prosthodontics for terminal defects of dental arches with the use of endosseous implants through electromyography.

Key words: terminal defects of dental arches, bridge prosthetics, intraosseous implants, functional state of masticatory muscles, electromyography.

Materials and Methods

Forty patients with terminal defects of dental arches after bridge prosthodontics with the use of endosseous implants were observed. Electromyographic studies were conducted on the masticatory and temporal muscles using a Neurotech (Russia) apparatus in both rest and maximal clenching conditions. The Neurotech software system was used on an IBM-compatible PC/AT 486 computer with Windows 95. The bioamplifier used in the hardware-software complex was a 4-channel electromyograph amplifier from Medikor. Standard plate electrodes were placed on the pre-degreased skin and secured with adhesive tape. After electrode placement, work began with the dialogue menu of the Neurotech software system. All patients were divided into 3 groups. Group 1 consisted of 12 patients with unilateral and bilateral terminal defects of dental arches, Group 2 included 14 patients after endosseous implantation, and Group 3 consisted of 14 patients who received bridge prostheses with distal support on dental implants.

Results of the Study

Comparing the functional activity of the temporal and masticatory muscles before orthopedic treatment in patients of Group 1 revealed the following pattern: on the intact side, the bioelectrical activity (BEA) of the masticatory muscles was 1.5 times higher, and of the temporal muscles 2.3 times higher, than on the defect side. The electrophysiological parameters of muscle activity in patients with bilateral terminal defects varied widely and depended on the chewing type. It should be noted that 80% of patients in this group showed a predominantly unilateral (right-sided) chewing type, and 20% had an even bilateral type. In patients with a unilateral chewing type, the average BEA values on the working side were 1.8 times higher for masticatory muscles and 2.1 times higher for temporal muscles. In patients with an even bilateral chewing type, BEA was approximately the same on both sides.

Electromyographic studies in patients of Group 2 showed the following dynamics in the bioelectrical activity of the masticatory muscles: during maximal

clenching, the maximum BEA amplitude was $440 \pm 120 \mu\text{V}$ in the masseter on the healthy side; $180 \pm 70 \mu\text{V}$ in the masseter on the edentulous side; $392 \pm 110 \mu\text{V}$ in the temporalis; and $728 \pm 191 \mu\text{V}$ in the temporalis on the healthy side. The coordination coefficient for masticatory muscles during chewing averaged 2.4 ± 0.13 , for temporal muscles 0.5 ± 0.13 ; at rest for masticatory muscles it was 0.4 ± 0.13 , and for temporal muscles 2.1 ± 0.13 , indicating muscle coordination issues. Three months after the implantation with early functional loading on the implant, there was a slight decrease in BEA at rest. On average, for masticatory muscles, the difference was 20% (masseter on the healthy side: $280 \pm 81 \mu\text{V}$, masseter on the edentulous side, near the implant: $190 \pm 5 \mu\text{V}$). For temporal muscles, BEA at rest decreased by 25%, with values being $450 \pm 11 \mu\text{V}$ on the edentulous side and $210 \pm 4 \mu\text{V}$ on the healthy side.

During clenching, BEA values were $460 \pm 98 \mu\text{V}$ for masseter on the healthy side and $397 \pm 143 \mu\text{V}$ on the edentulous side; for temporal muscles, $650 \pm 200 \mu\text{V}$ on the healthy side and $610 \pm 200 \mu\text{V}$ on the edentulous side. The coordination coefficient for masticatory muscles during clenching was 1.2 ± 0.08 , for temporal muscles 1.07 ± 0.06 . At rest, the coordination coefficient for masseter was 0.72 ± 0.05 and for temporalis 0.5 ± 0.03 . These changes in BEA reflect an improvement in the coordination of muscle work. After 12 months, patients in Group 3 exhibited ongoing normalization in the coordination of masticatory muscles. Electromyographic findings showed an increase in the activity of the masticatory muscles with early functional loading. The same pattern was observed in Group 2, though the process occurred more slowly, indicating adaptation of the masticatory musculature to orthopedic constructions and the reorganization of the BEA coordination.

Conclusion

The electromyographic studies confirmed the restoration of the functional state of the masticatory muscles during orthopedic treatment of patients with various defects in dental arches using dental implants. The

data obtained serve as objective evidence of the reorganization of reflex mechanisms of the muscle apparatus at different observation periods.

References

1. Gvetadze R.Sh. Evaluation of the bioelectrical activity of masticatory muscles depending on the implantation period // *Stomatology*. – 1999. – Vol. 78, No. 4. – pp. 43-44.
2. Gvetadze R.Sh., Amirkhanyan A.N. Functional restructuring of the dentoalveolar system during prosthetics with implant support // 4th All-Russian Scientific-Practical Conference. – Moscow, 2000. – pp. 161-162.
3. Gvetadze R.Sh., Matveeva A.A. Diagnosis and prediction of the functional state of the prosthetic bed tissues in dental implantology // *Problems of Dentistry and Neurostomatology*. – 1999. – No. 2. – pp. 38-40.
4. Dudko A.S., Shalatshina O.I., et al. Bioelectrical activity of masticatory muscles during prosthetics on dental implants // *New in Dentistry*. – 1994. – No. 3. – pp. 24-27.
5. Ivanova G.G., Akulov S.A. Changes in the tone of masticatory muscles before and during the treatment of secondary deformations of dental arches // *Collection of reactions of periodontal tissues and oral mucosa to dental materials*. – Moscow, 1990. – pp. 31-32.
6. Matveeva A.I., Shirina D.D., Dronov D.A. The role of clinical diagnostic methods in improving the effectiveness of treatment with implants // *Materials of the 5th International Conference of Maxillofacial Surgeons and Dentists*. – St. Petersburg, 2000. – pp. 86.
7. Matveeva A.I., Kulakov A.A. Complex diagnostic methods in dental implantation and possibilities of predicting treatment outcomes // *Medical Assistance*. – 1995. – No. 6. – pp. 14-17.
8. Sadykov M.I. Clinical-functional evaluation of the effectiveness of prosthetics for patients with complete edentulism using dental implants // *Stomatology*. – 2003. – No. 4. – pp. 52-54.